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SMALL CHANGES CAN MAKE A GREAT DIFFERENCE

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ABSTRACT

Four different types of commercially available silica nanoparticles were added to ordinary Portland cement pastes in order to study their effect. The subsequent multi-scale characterization of the material revealed that the addition of the nanoparticles induced a pozzolanic reaction that increased the amount of C-S-H gel of the paste in detriment of portlandite. This had important implications for the hydration kinetics and the micro-structure of the paste, resulting in an increase of the initial hydration rate. In addition, a reduction of the overall porosity was also observed. The C-S-H gel of the pastes with nanosilica showed also some particular features, like greater aluminum content and longer silicate chains. This was especially relevant because nanoindentation measurements and atomistic calculations showed that this was bound to an improvement in the mechanical properties of the C-S-H gel itself. Finally, the sum of all these factors resulted in pastes with a 30 % more compressive strength proving that, effectively, small changes can make a great difference.

INTRODUCTION

Amorphous silica has been added to cementitious materials for the last 20 years ⁽ⁱ⁾. Being mainly in the form of silica fume, silica induces a pozzolanic reaction that results in a reduction of the amount of CH of the paste. In addition, some researchers (1) have reported a diminution of the C/S of the resulting C-S-H gel which, by no doubt, should have an impact on its properties. However, the purity and the nature of the impurities of silica fume can vary greatly depending on its origin, affecting therefore the effect on the cement paste. In any case, purity is, on average, around 90 %. Something similar happens with the size of the particles. Although, it depends in the provider and the production method, they commonly have a mean diameter of 100 nm.

In the case of nanosilica, the dispersion of both the mean particle size values and purity is much smaller. This is mainly due to the fact that nanosilica is not an industrial byproduct as silica fume; although the production method, consisting usually in a sol gel process, has also a great influence. Generally, silica nanoparticles have a well defined diameter of 10-50 nm and a purity of almost 100 %. This reduced particle size is attained by the use of stabilizers in the dispersions which, in addition, serve to adjust the pH values. This is very important when they are added to the cement paste because they must be stable in very basic solutions. Sometimes, the nanoparticles are presented in the form of dry powders instead of colloidal dispersions. In such case, they tend to agglomerate, making the size of the agglomerates considerably bigger. However, the surface area is still large compared to that of silica fume. As a consequence of the difference in physical properties, silica nanoparticles are a lot more reactive than silica fume in spite of having the same chemical and structural composition ⁽ⁱⁱ⁾. Therefore, the reaction kinetics and the hydration products resulting from their addition to the cement paste might also vary.

The objective of this work is the study of the effect of the addition of silica nanoparticles to ordinary Portland cement pastes, with a focus in the C-S-H gel. This might increase the understanding on the nano-scale structure of the C-S-H gel, which is one of the most important unresolved issues in the field of cement research. Although proposing a new model would be outside of the scope of this work, the experimental results obtained might stimulate reflection and maybe even encourage some modification in the existing ones, see for example ^(iii, iv, v, vi).

EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

Sample preparation

Cement paste samples were prepared at a water-cement ratio (w/c) of 0.4 using an Ordinary Portland cement (CemI-52.5R) and 6 % by weight of cement of 4 different commercial nanosilicas, see Table 1. Extraordinarily, pastes with 3 and 18 wt.% of nanosilica were also prepared to study certain particular features. In the latter, the proportion of water had to be increased too to a water to binder ratio of 0.4. This was necessary in order to improve the otherwise very poor workability (qualitative) resulting from the addition of so a large amount of nanosilica. On the contrary, no superplasticizer was used in any case to avoid any possible interaction with the nanoparticles. Finally, one set of samples was also prepared without nanosilica as a reference (REF).

The mixing procedure was different for the pastes containing colloidal nanosilica (CS) than nanosilica powder (ADS). However, they were always kept as close as possible to that described by the standard UNE-En 196-1 (2005). In the first case, the colloidal dispersions were added directly to the water. Then, the solution was stirred for 5 minutes at 300 rpm prior to putting it together with the cement. On the contrary, the ADS powder was directly mixed with the cement for a minute at 300 rpm before pouring the water into it. The sequence of mixing of the paste was the same in all cases, consisting of two periods of one minute of stirring at 750 rpm separated by one minute of setting time. The samples were cast in steel prism moulds of $1 \times 1 \times 6 \text{ cm}^3$, and the molds were kept for 24 hours in a chamber at 20 °C and 100 % humidity. Then, they were demolded and placed in a saturated lime solution at room temperature for the next 27 days of curing.

Experimental techniques

It is evident that the macroscopic mechanical tests are one of the most interesting techniques from an engineering point of view ^(vii). In fact, they provide which is probably the most important parameter for most applications; the compressive strength. However, this type of techniques provides very little insight about what is going on in the material. Therefore, they have to be complemented by other materials science techniques. For instance, Hg intrusion porosimetry was used in this work to study the porosity distribution of the paste. Although it is well known that this technique overestimates the amount of the smaller porosity in detriment of the bigger one ^(viii), it was included to analyze the difference between samples.

The kinetics of the initial stages of the hydration process was studied by isothermal calorimetry. The measure consisted on sealing tightly about 1 g of paste inside a 1.3 ml glass ampoule and introducing it into the calorimeter (model 4200, Calorimetry Sciences Corporation). All runs were conducted at 20 °C with a time resolution of 1 minute. The very exothermic early rapid dissolution of cement was not accurately captured because it took 10 minutes for the temperature to stabilize from the moment the ampoule was introduced into the equipment.

The mineralogical composition of the pastes was analyzed by x-ray powder diffraction. The patterns were recorded on a Philips, X-Pert Pro diffractometer with graphite monochromator and Cu $K\alpha_1$ radiation. In this case, a representative portion of the paste had to be finely grounded and compacted to produce pellets of the appropriate dimensions for the tests.

The same procedure was employed for the preparation of ^{29}Si MAS-NMR specimens. In this case, the tests were run in a Bruker Avance DSX 300 and consisted in 90 ° pulses of 4.6 μs with high power decoupling, followed by a relaxation time of 3-4 s. Sample spinning around the magic angle took place at 7000 MHz, and the total number of pulses recorded was higher than 25000. This technique is very interesting for the study of cementitious materials because it provides information about the structure of the C-S-H gel ^(ix).

A depth sensing nanoindenter (model TI 900 Triboindenter, Hysitron Inc.) was used to study the mechanical properties of the C-S-H phase. The main shortcoming of this technique is that having the C-S-H gel a variable composition it is necessary to run a great number of tests in order to study the results statistically ^(x). In this work, more than 150 measurements were carried out on each sample. The tests were made in load-control mode and consisted in three loading-unloading cycles. However, only the final

unloading curve was considered. The load was adjusted so that the indentation depth was in the range 100-300 nm ^(xi). All curves with a maximum depth far away from these values were not considered. Also, the shape of the curves was carefully monitored and they were dismissed whenever they showed irregularities related to cracks or poor sample finishing ^(xii). In fact, sample preparation is very delicate because it involves high quality polishing. Furthermore, it is not clear the effect of surface roughness on the experimental results ^(xiii_xiv).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The first consequence of the addition of nanosilica to the cement paste was observed as soon as the hydration reactions began. The results of the calorimetry measurements showed initially an important acceleration in the reaction rate, see Figure 1. Furthermore, such acceleration increased with increasing amount of nanosilica added, in very good agreement with the findings reported by other researchers ^(xv-xvi). However, ten hours after the beginning of the test, the trend inverted. From this time until the end of the first day, the reference paste was the most exothermic and the one with 6 wt.% of nanosilica the least one. This behaviour was attributed in previous studies solely to the action of the nanoparticles as nucleation sites (15-16). Nevertheless, it seems reasonable to think that the great reactivity of the nanoparticles plays also an important role. In particular, nanosilica might react with the calcium dissolved from the cement grains avoiding the saturation of the solution and therefore favouring the dissolution. In any case, it should be noted that the area under the curves was approximately the same in all of them, what would indicate that the degree of hydration after 24 h was similar in all the pastes. After this time, all of them evolved at the same rate until the end of the experiment.

Since it is difficult to study the development of strength at very early ages, the first compression tests were run after 24 h from mixing, see Figure 2. The obtained results showed a general increase of strength in all the pastes containing nanosilica of about 50 % compared to the reference one (REF). As hydration went on, the development of strength continued in all samples although at different rates. After 7 days of curing, the difference in strength between the reference specimens and the pastes containing nanosilica was reduced to about a 40 %. This tendency was maintained along time and at the end of the curing process, 28 days, the samples with nanosilica were, on average, only 30 % stronger than REF. Furthermore, at this age a reference sample with the same water to binder ratio than the pastes with nanosilica was studied. The obtained compression strength value of 69.58 ± 1 MPa proved that the greater strength of the pastes with nanosilica compared to REF was not a consequence of their smaller water to solid ratio. The great difference of strength observed at very early ages and its reduction along the hydration process was in good agreement with the findings of other researchers (15-16) because it could be attributed to the accelerating effect of nanosilica. Nevertheless, such assumption would imply that in the long run all pastes would end up having similar strength values and this did not seem to be the case. In fact, the difference in compression strength between the reference sample and the ones containing nanosilica passed from ~ 10 MPa after 1 day of curing to ~ 20 MPa after 7 days, and more than ~ 30 MPa at the end of the curing process. However, it would be necessary to study the hydration process at much later ages to fully confirm the veracity of this assumption.

One of the parameters more directly influencing the strength and the resistance to chemical attack of the cement paste is the porosity. Figure 3 contains the total pore volume of all the samples after 24 hour and 28 days of curing. As can be observed in the figure, the samples with nanosilica were, in all cases, less porous than the reference one. Since the difference was very important, this could not be attributed only to one factor but to the combination of several ones. The most evident one was the greater water to binder ratio of the reference specimen (REF); although, as happened with the compression tests, the effect was very small. More important was the fact that the nanoparticles work as an ultra-fine filler, getting in the space between cement grains. Although they are too small to improve the packing efficiency by themselves, they serve as nucleation sites for the growth of hydration products around them. Therefore, it was the growth of such hydrates that actually reduced the porosity considerably.

Nevertheless, other factors like the pozzolanic reaction of nanosilica should also be considered (^{xvii_xviii}). The reason is that such reaction increases the amount of C-S-H gel in detriment of portlandite. Having a lamellar structure, portlandite tends to pack more loosely than the amorphous C-S-H gel. Furthermore, the amount of water by calcium atom required contained in the C-S-H gel is greater than in the case of portlandite. Therefore, the pozzolanic reaction increases the water demand. Finally, the accelerating effect of nanosilica might also affect the porosity. However, considering that the results of the calorimetry measurements showed a similar degree of hydration after 24 hours, this would be difficult to explain.

X-ray powder diffraction spectra confirmed the pozzolanic reaction of all the commercial nanosilicas used. However, a lot more information could be extracted from the results. In particular, the area of the portlandite peak at $2\theta=18.1^\circ$ was calculated to compare the relative proportion of such crystal phase present in every sample (^{xix_xx}). As can be observed in Figure 4, initially (1 day) the amount of portlandite present in REF and ADS was very similar and higher than in the other samples. After 7 days from mixing, ADS had already less portlandite than REF but still more than the pastes containing the colloidal dispersions. On the contrary, at the end of the curing process, ADS and CS3 were the pastes with the smallest amount of portlandite followed by CS1 and CS2. This late reaction of ADS can be attributed to two factors: on the one hand, to the poorer dispersion because of its powder nature and, on the other hand, to the bigger particle size. The latter was also the reason of the different behavior of CS3 compared to the other two colloidal dispersions. But portlandite is not the only crystal phase of interest. Comparison of the ettringite peaks of the pastes containing nanosilica and the reference specimens showed that there was also a difference, see Figure 5. Since both the difference and the intensity of the peaks were very small, it was necessary to increase the amount of nanosilica. The results presented in Figure show that the addition of nanosilica hinders the formation of ettringite. This can only be explained by the great reactivity of silica nanoparticles that favors the inclusion of aluminum atoms in the structure of the C-S-H gel.

The incorporation of aluminum within the structure of the C-S-H gel was further confirmed by ²⁹Si MAS-NMR. Although, the extent of the substitution is difficult to quantify because of the peak overlapping, it is clear from Figure 6 that the relative area of the small shoulder at -82 ppm ($Q^2(1Al)$) was smaller in REF than in the other specimens (^{xxi}). Such shoulder is generally attributed to the inclusion of aluminum into the bridging position of the silicate chains of the C-S-H gel (^{xxii, xxiii, xxiv}). Therefore, any variation on its relative area has an important impact in the average chain length of the C-S-H gel. Furthermore, assuming that aluminum incorporation results in merging of individual chains, this partially explains the increase of the relative area of the peak at -85 ppm (Q^2). Such peak is generally attributed to Si atoms in intermediate positions of the silicate chains, being its area directly related to the average chain length. However, the magnitude of the change was too large like have been solely induced by the aluminum. This was explained in terms of the great reactivity of nanosilica that increased the amount of silicon in the solution during the hydration process, promoting the formation of a C-S-H gel with longer silicate chains. Finally, it is possible to observe in Figure 6 that in all the specimens but the reference, there was initially a peak at about -110 ppm. Such peak was an evidence of the presence of unreacted nanosilica after 24 hours from mixing. Nevertheless, its complete disappearance after 28 days of curing suggests the complete reaction of the nanoparticles, contradicting the conclusions of other researchers (16).

A recent publication in the field of atomistic calculations of cement hydrates suggested that there is a relationship between the average chain length of the C-S-H gel and its mechanical properties (^{xxv}). However, this was in contradiction with the existing models which only correlate such mechanical properties with the porosity. Since nanosilica increases the average chain length of the C-S-H gel, it was decided to use depth sensing nanoindentation to study if this had any effect in its mechanical properties. Previous studies in this field (^{xxvi}) showed that the addition of 6 wt.% of nanosilica was not enough to have any effect in the properties of the C-S-H gel from a mechanical point of view. Nevertheless, considering the statistical nature of the technique, this might be simply a consequence of the lack of precision. Accordingly, it was decided to increase the amount of nanosilica to 18 wt.%. Table 2-3 contains the results obtained from the study of two pastes containing 6 and 18 wt.% of colloidal nanosilica. As can be observed in Table 2, nanosilica does not change the average values of the hardness and modulus of any of the phases of the C-S-H gel. On the contrary, it does modify the relative proportions of the two C-S-H phases, promoting the formation of the high-stiffness phase in detriment of the low-stiffness one, see Table 3. This is very interesting from a theoretical point of view, because it would confirm the results of the

atomistic calculations. Furthermore, assuming that the existing models are correct and the two C-S-H phases differ in the porosity values, it would imply that there is a relationship between the length of the silicate chains of the C-S-H gel and its porosity. Therefore, it might be expected that low stiffness C-S-H is made of dimers and the high stiffness one of pentamers. The next step would be trying to verify the existence of such relationship and explaining why this happens.

CONCLUSIONS

The addition of silica nanoparticles has proved, once again, to improve appreciably the performance of cement pastes in several aspects. On the one hand, silica nanoparticles act as nucleation sites for the growth of cement hydrates. This gives place to a reduction of the porosity of the paste and an early acceleration of the reaction rate, although the latter does not last long. In addition, the great reactivity and the pozzolanic nature of the nanoparticles further increase the reaction rate by reducing the amount of calcium ions in the hydration water. In any case, both processes are influenced by the particle size and the proper dispersion of the particles within the cement paste, being more effective the colloidal dispersions than the powder. Usually, aluminates are the most reactive phases of cement. However, in the presence of nanosilica, silicon ions are also available from the very beginning, making easier the incorporation of aluminum atoms into the structure of the C-S-H gel. This is one of the reasons for the longer silicate chains of the C-S-H gel in pastes with nanosilica. The other one is that nanosilica itself promotes merging of the silicate chains increasing it further. Such modification of the structure of the C-S-H gel has important implications in the mechanical properties of the C-S-H gel, resulting in an increase of the relative volume of the high-stiffness C-S-H gel in detriment of the low density one. The sum of all these factors results in stronger and more durable pastes. Therefore, it is possible to say that sometimes small changes can make a big difference.

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TABLE 1 Physicochemical properties of the Nanoparticles

Name	Particle Size (nm)	pH	Stabilizing Agent	SiO₂ Content (wt.%)	Presentation
CS1	30	10	Na ₂ O	45	Colloid
CS2	20	10	Na ₂ O	40	Colloid
CS3	120	9.5	NH ₃	20	Colloid
ADS	1400 ^a	-	-	95	Powder

^a The given value corresponds to the agglomerated grain size, being the individual particle size 15nm.

- Not applicable

TABLE 2 Nanoindentation modulus (E) and hardness (H) of two samples containing 6 wt.%, and 18 wt.% of nanosilica.

	<u>Low-Stiffness C-S-H gel</u>		<u>High-Stiffness C-S-H Gel</u>	
	E (GPa)	H (GPa)	E (GPa)	H (GPa)
6 wt.%	17±1	0.53±0.02	23.7±0.7	0.76±0.01
18 wt.%	18.9±0.4	0.56±0.02	26.7±0.8	0.95±0.02

TABLE 3 Relative volumes of the two C-S-H phases calculated from the nanoindentation modulus (Vol_E) and hardness (Vol_H) of two samples containing 6 wt.%, and 18 wt.% of nanosilica.

	<u>Low-Stiffness C-S-H gel</u>		<u>High-Stiffness C-S-H Gel</u>	
	Vol_E (%)	Vol_H (%)	Vol_E (%)	Vol_H (%)
6 wt.%	44±14	47±6	37±14	38±3
18 wt.%	38±6	41±3	50±7	47±3

FIGURE 1 Calorimetry tests of pastes with 0, 3, and 6 wt.% of nanosilica.

FIGURE 2 Compressive strength as a function of the time from mixing.

FIGURE 3 Porosity values obtained by Hg intrusion porosimetry at different times.

FIGURE 4 Area of the portlandite peak at $2\theta=18.1^\circ$.

FIGURE 5 X-ray diffraction spectra of pastes containing 0, 6, and 18 wt.% of nanosilica after 24 hours from mixing.

FIGURE 6 ^{29}Si MAS-NMR spectra after 24 hours (left) and 28 days of curing (right).